

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

**Omonov Sardor
Ulmasovich**

PhD, TSUE

**Zoitov Javlon
Zokirovich**

master, BFA

New economic relations are formed between the public and the private sector in the condition of market economy. One of such economic relations in the practice of developed countries is the public-private partnership (PPP). Today the main aspects of the public-private partnership should be learnt deeply such as essence, features, principles, history of development, legal basis of public-private partnership in the countries of the world and its development in our country. Moreover, usage of digital technologies in the public-private partnership is one of the main aspects these days, so it is crucial to learn digital technologies in the public-private partnership.

Today the government are paying attention to the public-private partnership in order to increase the economy, so several legal documents are being adopted these years. For instance, the Law № 537 of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the public-private partnership”, the Resolution № 259 of the Cabinet of Ministry of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On improving the implementation of public-private partnership projects” are helpful to develop the public and private relations. According to the legislature of our country, public-private partnership is a partnership between a public partner and a private partner based on the consolidation of their resources for the implementation of a legally formalized public-private partnership project for a certain period of time¹.

Additionally, the Resolution № 259 of the Cabinet of Ministry of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On improving the implementation of public-private partnership projects” includes the followings:

- initiating, developing and selecting public-private partnership projects;
- establishment of the procedure for initial evaluation of public-private partnership projects;
- preparation of the concept of the public-private partnership project;
- maintaining a report on the implementation of public-private partnership projects;

¹ The Law № 537 of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the public-private partnership”, Article 3, Tashkent, 10.05.2019; <https://www.lex.uz/docs/-4329270>

- maintaining a register of public-private partnership projects².

Today the main types of public-private partnerships that currently exist in the world are:

- service agreement;
- management agreement;
- lease or lease agreement;
- contract for construction, commissioning and delivery of the project or similar agreements (mainly in the field of construction);
- concession agreement;
- agreements of joint ventures, etc.

For governments, public-private partnerships (PPPs) in science, technology and innovation (STI) can help make research and innovation policy more responsive to the changing nature of innovation and to social and global challenges. For business, partnering with public research can help solve problems, develop new markets or generate value through co-operation and co-production³. In addition, today digital technologies are also important in the public-private partnership process. It is helpful to ease the projects in the public-private partnership with digital technologies. Investors can be attracted more than sample projects in the public-private partnership projects with digital technologies.

² The Resolution № 259 of the Cabinet of Ministry of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On improving the implementation of public-private partnership projects”, Tashkent, 26.04.2020; <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4798603>

³ www.oecd-ilibrary.org – the website of Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development; https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/sti_in_outlook-2016-10-en.pdf?expires=1607746819&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=1396DF70EC196DA4249B957D3F191057